

Ethnomedicine for Women Problems by the Tribes of Khammam District, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract- The paper deals with 54 species of plants covering 36 families used by the tribals of Khammam district, Andhra Pradesh, for curing women diseases. Trees are dominant with 19 species. Fabaceae is represented by a maximum of six species. A maximum of 21 species are used for the treatment of leucorrhoea followed by fertility (7 spp.). Twenty seven practices were found to be new.

Keywords: Abortion, Contraceptive, Easy delivery, Fertility, Leucorrhoea, Post-partum problems

I. INTRODUCTION

Khammam district is surrounded by Chhattisgarh and Odisha states in the North, Krishna district in the South, East and West Godavari districts in the East and Nalgonda and Warangal districts in the West. The geographical coordinates of the district falls within the longitudes of 79°47' and 81°47' E and the latitudes of 16°45' and 18°35' N occupying an area of 16, 029 Sq km with a total forest area of 7, 594.38 sq km. The tribal population of India is 8.2% and Andhra Pradesh has 7.0% tribal population. Khammam district with 26.47% tribal population stands first in the state (Census, 2011) and is the home of six tribal communities, viz., Koya, Lambada, Gond/Naikpod, Yerukula, Nayak and Konda Reddi. Though there are publications on ethnomedicine dealing with a variety of diseases not much information is available on women diseases necessitating the present study.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethnobotanical survey was conducted in tribal rich habitations of Khammam district once in every two months from 2008 to 2012 with a duration of 10-15 days. About 4-7 days were spent during each trip with different tribal communities in their dwellings. After establishing good rapport with them, the utility of plants and detailed methods of uses were documented. In 102 pockets of the study area, 102 *vaidhyas* and practitioners were consulted. Data collected were cross checked with the data obtained from same as well as on different settlement on different occasions for authenticity. Voucher specimens were collected in both flowering and fruiting stages, herbarium specimens were prepared and deposited in the Herbarium of the Department of Botany, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam (AUV), after identification.

III. ENUMERATION

The plants are enumerated alphabetically with valid botanical name followed by family, vernacular name, English name, locality, collector and voucher number. Each ethno-medicinal practice is provided with the part(s) used, method of preparation, mode of administration, dosage and the tribal informant. Plants and practices marked with an asterisk (*) are considered to be new or less known.

Abelmoschus moschatus Medik. Malvaceae VN: Yerra benda E: Musk mallow Bethampudi RRM 10038

Leucorrhoea: Thirty ml of whole plant decoction is administered twice a day for 10 days. Lambada

Ananas comosus (L.) Merr. Bromeliaceae VN: Anasa E: Pineapple Gummadi Doddi RRM 10037

Abortion: Thirty ml of fruit juice is taken orally once without taking food or 20 ml of leaf juice is taken once. Gond

Aristolochia bracteolata Lam. Aristolochiaceae VN: Gadidagapa E: Bracted birth wort Peruru RRM 10169

Leucorrhoea: Stem and black pepper are ground and two spoonful of paste is taken along with rice washed water once a day for 5-10 days. Koya

Azadirachta indica A. Juss. Meliaceae VN: Vepa E: Powdered talk Madupalli RRM 10144

Contraceptive: Two spoonful of seed oil is administered after fourth day of menstrual cycle once a day for 5-6 days. Yerukula

Azanza lampas (Cav.) Alef. Malvaceae VN: Konda patti E: Ran-bendi Tekulapalem RRM 10469

***Leucorrhoea:** Thirty ml of whole plant decoction mixed in a cup of water is taken twice a day till cure. Konda Reddi

Borassus flabellifer L. Arecaceae VN: Tadi E: Great fan plam Eravendi RRM 10015

***Easy delivery:** Root is tied over the waist at the time of delivery. Nayak

Brassica nigra (L.) Czern. Brassicaceae VN: Aavalu E: True mustard Yerram Padu RRM 10115

Antisterility: Ten ml of root decoction is administered daily once for 3-5 days. Gond

Butea monosperma (Lam.) Kuntze Fabaceae VN: Moduga E: Flame of the forest Thungaram RRM 10116

Easy delivery: One spoonful of seed powder mixed with one spoonful of ghee and honey is administered before pains. Koya

Capparis sepiaria L. Capparaceae VN: Nalla uppi, E: Caper Chinnamunagala RRM 10017

***Post-partum problems:** Root bark along with that of *Tamarindus indica* and stem bark of *Holoptelea integrifolia* is made into decoction. Three spoonful of decoction is administered twice a day for 3 days. Konda Reddi

Careya arborea Roxb. Barringtoniaceae VN: Goodareni chekka E: Patana oak Ramakrishnapuram RRM 10047

***Post-partum problems:** Ten ml of flower juice mixed with one spoon of sugar syrup is taken once a day till cure. Nayak

Ceiba pentandra (L.) Gaertn. Bombacaceae VN: Tella buruga E: White silk cotton tree Gowridevipeta RRM 10194

***Leucorrhoea:** Ten ml of root decoction is administered once a day till cure. Gond

Cissus quadrangularis L. Vitaceae VN: Nalleru E: Adamant creeper

Lakshminpuram RRM 10157

***Leucorrhoea:** Two spoonful of stem juice is taken twice a day for 15-20 days. Gond

Citrullus colocynthis (L.) Schrad. Cucurbitaceae VN: Erripuchcha E: Bitter apple

Bethampudi RRM 10192

Abortion: Ten ml of root juice is taken with a spoon of honey once a day for 3 days. Konda Reddi

Cocos nucifera L. Arecaceae VN: Kobbari chettu E: Coconut Paleru RRM 10088

Leucorrhoea: Root decoction is administered in 30 ml dose once a day till cure. Yerukula

Crotalaria laburnifolia L. Fabaceae VN: Giligicha kaya E: Ratted weed Peddanallabelli RRM 10096

***Labour pains:** Three spoonful of seed powder is administered along with a glass of water. Gond

Crotalaria verrucosa L. Fabaceae VN: Giligicha, E: Wild jute Chinnanallabelli RRM 10100

***Easy delivery:** Ten g of seed paste mixed with a cup of water is given. Konda Reddi

Curcuma aromatica Salisb. Zingiberaceae VN: Kasthuri dumpa, E: Wild turmeric Peruru RRM 10226

***Leucorrhoea:** Five g of tuber paste is taken orally once a day for 10 days. Koya

Dendrophthoe falcata (L. f.) Ettingsh. VN: Bajanica E: Mistletoe

Loranthaceae Lakshminpuram RRM 10378

***Antisterility:** Take equal quantities of stem along with stem bark of *Ficus racemosa* and made into powder is administered twice a day before the start of menstrual cycle for 7 days. Nayak

Diplocyclos palmatus (L.) Jeffrey Cucurbitaceae VN: Pinna chettu E: Lollipop

Chikupalli RRM 10252

Fertility: One spoonful of seed paste is given along with a cup of water before menstrual cycle once a day for 3 days. Gond

Distimake aegyptius (L.) A.R. Simoes & Staples Convolvulacea VN: Eluka chevi aku E: Buck bean
Muttagudem RRM 10268

***Fertility:** Ten ml of leaf juice mixed with 20 ml of sugarcane juice is administered once a day for 3-5 days.
Konda Reddi

Dregea volubilis (L.f.) Benth. ex Hook.f. (*Wattakaka volubilis* (L. f.) Stapf Asclepiadaceae VN: Barre
sugandhipala, E: Cotton milk plant Charla RRM 10489

***Leucorrhoea:** Two spoonful of root decoction is taken once a day for 15 days. Konda Reddi

Euphorbia heterophylla L. Euphorbiaceae VN: Osso E: Marieclaire

Edugurallapalli RRM 10291

***Leucorrhoea:** Thirty ml of leaf decoction is taken twice a day for 15 days. Gond

Ficus benghalensis L. Moraceae VN: Marri E: Banyan tree

Mamuluru RRM 10261

Fertility: Five gm of tender prop root paste mixed with one spoonful of crystal sugar, half spoon of cumin seeds and curd is kept in a pot and exposed to sunlight is administered once a day. Nayak

Ficus hispida L.f. Moraceae VN: Brahma medi E: Wild fig Chiruthapalli RRM 10331

***Leucorrhoea:** Stem bark and roots taken in equal quantities are made into decoction and 30 ml dose is taken once a day till cure. Gond

Ficus racemosa L. Moraceae VN: Medi E: Gular fig Dummugudem RRM 10365

***Easy delivery:** Two spoonful of root decoction is administered at the time of labor pains. Lambada

Ficus virens Aiton Moraceae VN: Banda juvvi E: Maiden hair tree

Soraveedu RRM 10243

Leucorrhoea: Thirty ml of stem bark decoction mixed with a cup of rice washed water is administered twice a day till cure. Konda Reddi

Hemidesmus indicus (L.) R.Br. Periplocaceae VN: Chinna guda pala E. Indian sarsa

Mukundapuram RRM 10280

***Fertility:** Root paste mixed with cow ghee is administered in one spoonful once a day for 2 days. Nayak

Lagerstroemia speciosa (L.) Pers. Lythraceae VN: Vara gogu E: Pride of India, Queen of the flowers Peruru RRM 10317

Post-partum problems: Ten ml of root decoction is administered twice a day for 3 days. Konda Reddi

Lannea coromandelica (Houtt.) Merr. Anacardiaceae VN: Gumpena E: Indian ash tree Soraveedu RRM 10383

***Leucorrhoea:** Three gm of dried gum is taken along with half spoon of butter twice a day till cure. Yerukula

Madhuca indica J.F. Gmel. Sapotaceae VN: Ippa chettu E: Indian butter tree

Bayyaram RRM 10208

Fertility: Stem bark along with those of *Murraya koenigii* and *Bauhinia racemosa* are ground with water, filtered and sugar is added and 100 gm is administered once a day for 3 days. Yerukula

Magnolia champaca (L.) Baill. ex Pierre Magnoliaceae VN: Sampangi E: Yellow champ Soraveedu RRM 10309

***Post-partum problems:** Leaves and cumin seeds taken in equal quantities are pestled and plastered on the head with cow ghee. Lambada

Mimosa pudica L. Fabaceae VN: Atti patthi E: Touch me not Peruru RRM 10267

Leucorrhoea: Sun dried whole plant is powdered and made into tablets. One tablet is taken orally once a day till cure. Koya

Monoon longifolium (Sonn.) B.Xue & R.M.K. Saunders Annonaceae VN: Asokam E: Cemetery tree Bethampudi RRM 10420

Leucorrhoea: Thirty ml of root decoction is administered twice a day for 10 days. Nayak

Musa paradisiaca L. Musaceae VN: Arati E: Plantain Peruru RRM 10372

Leucorrhoea: One spoonful of root juice is administered twice a day till cure. Konda Reddi

Nelumbo nucifera Gaertn. Nelumbonaceae VN: Tamara E: Sacred lotus Bhadrachalam RRM 10294

Leucorrhoea: Two spoonful of petiole juice mixed with a cup of curd is administered once a day for 10 days. Lambada

Ocimum americanum L. Lamiaceae VN: Kukka tulasi E: Common basil

Thaliperu RRM 10371

***Easy delivery:** Leaf paste is applied on the abdomen. Yerukula

Ocimum tenuiflorum L. Lamiaceae VN: Krishna tulasi E: Holy basil

Thaliperu RRM 10233

***Contraceptive:** Thirty ml of leaf juice is administered after fourth day of menstrual cycle once a day for 5-6 days. Lambada

Pachygone ovata (Poir.) Miers. ex Hook. f. & Thomson Menispermaceae VN: Pedda dhusari teega E: Diels Chiruthapalli RRM 10302

***Leucorrhoea:** Two spoonful of leaf juice is administered early in the morning once a day till cure. Konda Reddi

Pergularia daemia (Forssk.) Chiov. Asclepiadaceae VN: Dustapu teega E: Whitflow plant Vajedu RRM 10367

Abortion: One spoonful of leaf paste mixed with one spoon of hingh is administered once a day for 2-3 days. Yerukula

Phyllanthus acidus (L.) Skeels Euphorbiaceae VN: Rasa usiri E: Country gooseberry Perur RRM 10401

***Gynaecological complaints:** Twenty ml of fruit juice mixed with one spoon of crystal sugar is taken twice a day till cure. Yerukula

Plumbago zeylanica L. Plumbaginaceae VN: Tella chitramulam E: Ceylon leads wort Thaliperu RRM 10445

***Contraceptive:** Root and *hingh* are taken in equal quantities and pestled and half spoon of paste with a cup of water is taken from the fourth day of menstrual cycle once a day for 9 days. Nayak

Putranjiva roxburghii Wall. Euphorbiaceae VN: Putram jeva E: Child-life tree Chiruthapalli RRM 10478

For male child: Two gm of seed powder is taken along with a cup of water once a day for 3 days. Konda Reddi

To arrest child mortality: Two spoonful of seed powder is taken with a cup of water for 20 days during pregnancy. Gond

Ricinus communis L. Euphorbiaceae VN: Amudamu E: Castor oil tree Vissapuram RRM 10492

***Breast swelling:** Leaf paste is applied on the affected areas till cure. Yerukula

Sapindus emarginatus Vahl Sapindaceae VN: Kunkudu E: Soapnut Chikupalli RRM 10464

***Easy delivery:** Fruit juice is applied around the vagina. Konda Reddi

Smilax zeylanica L. Smilacaceae VN: Konda thambera gadda E: Rough bind weed Yetapaka RRM 10447

Fertility: One spoonful of root paste mixed with one cup of rice washed water is administered once a day for 3 days. Gond

***Solanum americanum* Mill. (*nigrum* L.)** Solanaceae VN: Nallbuddakasi E: Black night shade Tekulapalem RRM 10452

Anti-sterility: Thirty ml of leaf juice is taken after fourth day of menstrual cycle once a day for 9 days. Konda Reddi

Tamarindus indica L. Fabaceae VN: Chinthu chettu E: Tamarind tree Tekulapalem RRM 10437

Leucorrhoea: One spoonful of seed powder is administered with rice washed water twice a day for 15 days. Nayak

Tephrosia purpurea (L.) Pers. Fabaceae VN: Vempali E: Wild indigo Bayyaram RRM 10418

Leucorrhoea: Whole plant decoction is administered in doses of 15 ml daily twice for 3 days. Koya

Tinospora cordifolia (Willd.) Hook.f. & Thomson Menispermaceae VN: Tippa teega E: Gulancha tinospora Edugurallapalli RRM 10476

Leucorrhoea: Whole plant decoction in 30 ml dose is administered twice a day for 10 days. Konda Reddi

Typha angustifolia L. (*Typha angustata* Bory & Chaub.) Typhaceae VN: Jammu gaddi, Thunga E: Cat tail Chikupalli RRM 10513

***Leucorrhoea:** One spoonful of root decoction mixed with one glass of rice washed water is taken twice a day for 10 days. Konda Reddi.

Vanda tessellata (Roxb.) Hook. ex G. Don Orchidaceae VN: Vajanika E: Ichneumon plant Vajedu RRM 10516

***To beget children:** Leaf is made into amulet and tied around the neck on the day of *Revathi star* to beget children. Nayak

Vitex negundo L. Verbenaceae VN: Vavilaku E: Negundo Laksmanapuram RRM 10434

Post-natal care: Leaves are boiled in water and bath is taken with this water. Gond

Withania somnifera (L.) Dunal Solanaceae VN: Aswagandha E: Aswagandha Tekulapalem RRM 10494

Fertility: Ten ml of root decoction along with a cup of milk is administered once a day for 7 days. Gond

Wrightia tinctoria (Roxb.) R. Br. Apocynaceae VN: Ankudu E: Sweet indraja Peruru RRM 10471

Labour pains: Latex is applied on the stomach at the time of delivery. Konda Reddi

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The paper deals with 54 species of plants covering 49 genera and 36 families used by the tribals of Khammam district, Andhra Pradesh, for curing women diseases viz., abortion, anti-sterility, beget children, breast swelling, child mortality, contraceptive, easy delivery, fertility, gynecological complaints, labor pains, leucorrhoea, male child and post-natal care. Habit-wise analysis showed the dominance of trees with 19 species followed by shrubs and herbs (15 spp. each), and climbers (5 spp.). Fabaceae is the dominant family with six species followed by Moraceae, Euphorbiaceae (4 spp. each.), Malvaceae, Arecaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Asclepiadaceae, Solanaceae, Lamiaceae, Menispermaceae (2 spp. each) and others with one species each. For the treatment of leucorrhoea 21 species are employed followed by fertility (7 spp.); easy delivery (6 spp.); post-partum problems (4 spp.); abortion, contraceptive, antisterility (3 spp. each); labour pains (2 spp.), gynaecological complaints, male child, to beget children, arrest child mortality, post-natal care, and breast swelling (one spp. each). Of the total 55 practices 27 were found to be new or less known (Jain and Jain, 2016). Research work on menstrual disorders of Khammam district was already published (Manjula et al., 2015).

Plants used for similar purpose in different parts of India, Bangladesh and Pakistan are *Aristolochia bracteolata*, *Withania somnifera* by the herbal vendors living in Delhi (Sinha, 1991); *Aristolochia bracteolata*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Brassica nigra*, *Citrullus colocynthis*, *Ocimum tenuiflorum* by Nakkala, Irula, Yerukala, Sugali, Chenchu tribes of Chittoor district, Andhra Pradesh (Vedavathy et al., 1997); *Diplocyclos palmatus*, *Ficus benghalensis*, *Withania somnifera* by the folklore of Shahjahanpur district, Uttar Pradesh (Sharma, 2000); *Citrullus colocynthis* by the people of Lakhimpur district, Assam (Das and Saikia, 2002); *Crotalaria verrucosa* by Andha, Bhil, Kolam tribes of Yavatmal district, Maharashtra (Bhogaonkar and Kadam, 2006); *Withania*

somnifera by Bhotia, Banrawat, Tharu, Jaunsari tribes of Uttaranchal (Arya and Agarwal, 2006); *Diplocyclos palmatus* by Andha, Bhil, Kolam, Banjara tribes of Yavatmal district, Maharashtra (Bhogaonkar and Kadam, 2006); *Withania somnifera* by the people of Solan district, Himachal Pradesh (Verma and Chauhan, 2006); *Mimosa pudica* by Bodo, Kachari, Rabha, Garo tribes of Darrang district, Assam (Nath et al., 2007); *Diplocyclos palmatus* by the Maldharis of Junagadh district, Gujarat (Punjani, 2007); *Azadirachta indica*, *Careya arborea*, *Pergularia daemia* by Kandha, Ganda, Sabara tribes of Kalahandi district, Orissa (Panda and Padhy, 2008); *Ficus benghalensis*, *Smilax zeylanica* by Konda reddy, Konda dora, Koya dora, Konda kammara, Konda kapu, Manne dora, Valmiki tribes of East Godavari district, Andhra Pradesh (Suneetha et al., 2009); *Plumbago zeylanica* by Chakma. Marmu, Tripura tribes of Chittagong Hill tracts of Bangladesh (Biswas et al., 2010), *Vitex negundo* by the ethnic people of Medak district, Andhra Pradesh (Reddy et al., 2010), *Ficus virens*, *Musa paradisiaca*, *Withania somnifera* by Gond, Kol, Baiga, Panica, Khaiwar, Manjhi, Mawasi, Agaria tribes of Rewa district, Madhya Pradesh (Shukla et al., 2010); *Mimosa pudica* by Bhilla tribe of Maharashtra (Kamble et al., 2010), *Abelmoschus moschatus*, *Tinospora cordifolia* by Bhil tribe of Ratlam district, Madhya Pradesh (Jadhav, 2010); *Ananas comosus*, *Aristolochia bracteolata* by Konda reddy tribes of Andhra Pradesh (Raju et al., 2010); *Aristolochia bracteolata* by Savara, Jatapu, Gadaba, Konda dora, Kuttiya, Yerukula tribes of Srikakulam district, Andhra Pradesh (Naidu et al., 2011); *Ananas comosus*, *Citrullus colocynthis*, *Pergularia daemia* by the tribes of East Godavari district, Andhra Pradesh (Suneetha et al., 2012); *Pergularia daemia*, *Tinospora cordifolia* by the Khond, Porja, Gadaba, Savara, Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTG) of Visakhapatnam district, Andhra Pradesh (Rao et al., 2012); *Pergularia daemia*, *Smilax zeylanica* by Bhunja, Kandha, Gand, Banjara, Sabar, Bhottada, Dal tribes of Kalahandi district, Odisha (Mallik et al., 2012); *Withania somnifera* by people of Dera Ghazi Khan district, Pakistan (Gulshan et al., 2012); *Ananas comosus*, *Aristolochia bracteolata*, *Diplocyclos palmatus*, *Ficus hispida*, *Ficus racemosa*, *Madhuca indica*, *Nelumbo nucifera*, *Pergularia daemia*, *Sapindus emarginatus*, *Withania somnifera* by Bagata, Gadaba, Goudu, Khond, Konda dora, Konda kammara, Kotia, Mali, Mukha dora, Porja, Valmiki tribes of Visakhapatnam district, Andhra Pradesh (Babu et al., 2014); *Ananas comosus* by the people of Narsingdi district, Bangladesh (Rahman and Debnath, 2015); *Withania somnifera* by Gond, Madia, Pardhan, Kawar tribes of Gadrochi district, Maharashtra (Bhogaonkar and Saudagar, 2016); *Hemidesmus indicus*, *Musa paradisiaca*, *Tinospora cordifolia* the Lodha tribes of by Paschim Medinipur, Jhargram, Bankura, Purulia, Alipurduar, South 24 Paraganas districts of West Bengal West Bengal (Chaudhury et al., 2016); *Diplocyclos palmatus* by Savara, Jatapu, Gadaba, Konda dora, Kuttiya, Yerukula tribes of Srikakulam district, Andhra Pradesh (Naidu and Reddi, 2018); *Dendrophthoe falcata*, *Vitex negundo* Gonds, Kolams, Koyas, Lambadas, Mannes, Naikpods, Pradhans, Thoties, Yerukalas tribes of Adilabad district, Andhra Pradesh (Swamy and Reddi, 2020). The ethnobotanical claims emanating from the present survey need to be subjected to pharmaco-chemical studies in order to discover their true potential.

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